

Rehabilitation of Cognitive Communication and Swallowing Impairment in Traumatic Brain Injury- A Case Report

1. Ms. Pavithra Ravi

*Clinical Supervisor Grade 1, Department of Audiology and Speech-Language Pathology,
SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, SRM Nagar, Potheri, Chengalpattu, Tamil Nadu*

2. Ms. Vandhana. P

*Clinical Supervisor Grade 1, Department of Audiology and Speech-Language Pathology,
SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, SRM Nagar, Potheri, Chengalpattu, Tamil Nadu*

3. Ms. Divya. S

*Assistant professor, Department of Audiology and Speech-Language Pathology,
SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, SRM Nagar, Potheri, Chengalpattu, Tamil Nadu*

Corresponding Author:

Ms. Vandhana. P

*Clinical Supervisor Grade 1, Department of Audiology and Speech-Language Pathology,
SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, SRM Nagar, Potheri, Chengalpattu, Tamil Nadu*

Abstract:

This case study chronicles the comprehensive management of a 34-year-old male admitted to the neurology ICU after a severe traumatic brain injury (TBI) resulting from a road traffic accident. The patient underwent emergent cranioplasty and required tracheostomy and ventilatory support due to associated respiratory compromise. Following stabilization, he was evaluated for speech and swallowing deficits. Cognitive and oromuscular impairments were initially profound, complicating assessment and therapy initiation. Over several weeks, a structured rehabilitation program incorporating cognitive training, passive range of motion exercises, and swallowing manoeuvres was implemented. The patient progressed to successful tracheostomy decannulation and nasogastric tube removal, achieving significant functional gains both in communication and swallowing function.

Key words: Neurology, Traumatic Brain Injury, Dysphagia,

Introduction:

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) is a prominent contributor to global mortality and disability rates, exerting significant adverse effects on both societal and economic fronts.(1)TBI is primarily caused by traffic accidents, falls, and assaults. (2) TBI can cause a range of difficulties with behaviour, cognitive processes, and physical functions—all of which are critical for swallowing processes.

Post-TBI patients may experience biomechanical deficits affecting the oral, pharyngeal, and oesophageal portions of the swallowing process, which is generally classified into three parts. In these individuals, swallowing may be impacted by a variety of processes since food needs to be transported securely from the mouth to the stomach. In addition to cognitive and behavioural deficiencies that may impact swallowing, brain traumas may impede swallowing mechanics, making it challenging to diagnose and treat this disorder (2)

According to Morgan et al. (3), the degree of brain damage correlates with an increased prevalence of swallowing difficulties. In the acute care context, they found that 68% of the seriously brain-damaged patients had dysphagia (3). The severity of the damage on CT, lower Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) and Rancho Los Amigos (RLA) scores upon admission, aberrant tongue control, the existence of a tracheostomy, feeding tubes, and mechanical ventilation for more than two weeks are risk factors for developing dysphagia after a brain injury. (4) Nonetheless, many patients with dysphagia experience favourable evolution, and 75–94% of them regain their capacity to eat orally (3,5). After a traumatic brain injury (TBI), dysphagia should be evaluated and treated as soon as possible to prevent consequences such as aspiration pneumonia and malnourishment (6).

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) often leads to complex neurological deficits, including cognitive impairment, speech-language challenges, and swallowing disorders. This case report details the rehabilitation journey of a 34-year-old male who sustained severe TBI necessitating intensive care and specialized speech-language pathology (SLP) interventions. The focus is on the integration of cognitive communication therapy and swallowing interventions to promote functional recovery and readiness for decannulation in the ICU setting.

Case Presentation:

A 34-year-old male presented to the neurology ICU following a road traffic accident resulting in extensive fronto-parietal injury and acute medullary hemorrhage. Emergency cranioplasty was performed to alleviate intracranial pressure, followed by tracheostomy placement due to respiratory compromise. Initial management included intravenous medications and nasogastric (NG) tube feeding, complicated by right-sided unilateral hemiparesis affecting physical mobility.

Speech-Language and Swallowing Assessment:

After 10 days in ICU, the patient underwent a thorough SLP assessment, and the client exhibited intermittent confusion with preserved awareness initially hindered evaluation. Oromuscular weakness, including restricted lip and tongue range of motion were noted. As cognitive stability improved, passive range of motion exercises were initiated to enhance muscle tone.

Subsequent cognitive assessments using the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) identified deficits in attention, memory, executive functions, and expressive language skills. Therapy sessions focused on auditory comprehension, environmental sound awareness, and verbal responsiveness.

Clinical swallow examination and Fiberoptic Endoscopic Evaluation of Swallowing (FEES) revealed poor laryngeal elevation, aspiration risk, and nocturnal oxygen desaturation due to salivary aspiration. Interventions included muscle isotonic exercises targeting lip, tongue, and jaw muscles, alongside base of tongue exercises to enhance bolus control. Sensory stimulation techniques and cognitive-linguistic tasks were integrated to promote swallow reflexes and cognitive engagement during therapy sessions.

With advancing cognitive and swallowing recovery, trials of cuff deflation were initiated to assess readiness for ventilatory weaning, progressing from 5 to 15 minutes per day.

Intervention and its outcome:

Cognitive Linguistic training:

Cognitive linguistic training tasks play a pivotal role in the rehabilitation of individuals with traumatic brain injury (TBI) by addressing a wide range of cognitive and communication deficits. These tasks are meticulously designed to target specific cognitive domains that are commonly impaired following TBI, including attention, memory, executive functions, and language skills.

Firstly, activities such as orientation questions are crucial as they help patients regain awareness of themselves and their surroundings, which can be significantly compromised after a brain injury. This foundational awareness lays the groundwork for further cognitive and functional recovery.

1. Orientation Questions: Asking simple questions to assess orientation to person, place, and time (e.g., "Can you tell me your name?", "Do you know where you are right now?").

2. Following Simple Commands: Instructing the patient to perform basic actions (e.g., "Close your eyes," "Raise your right hand").

3. Verbal Response Tasks: Asking the patient to respond verbally to questions or prompts to assess language comprehension and production (e.g., "What day is it today?", "Tell me the last thing you ate.").

4. Word Finding Tasks: Providing cues for the patient to name objects or items within their immediate environment (e.g., "Can you name this object?" while showing a common item).

5. Memory Recall Tasks: Asking the patient to recall recent events or information (e.g., "Can you tell me what happened earlier today?" or "Who visited you yesterday?").

6. Simple Problem-Solving Scenarios: Presenting basic scenarios that require logical thinking and verbal reasoning (e.g., "If you have a headache, what would you do?").

Facilitatory techniques were initiated to elicit the swallow reflex often involve sensory stimulation, tailored to address specific deficits such as delayed or absent swallow response. Thermal stimulation targets the anterior faucial pillars, recognized as sensitive areas that can trigger the swallow reflex. Gustatory stimulation also employed sour or spicy boluses or substances like capsaicin, which have been shown to facilitate the swallow response. This approach is particularly beneficial for this client with reduced oral sensitivity or those experiencing delays in initiating the swallow reflex. These sensory techniques are integral components of dysphagia therapy, aiming to enhance the neural pathways involved in swallowing and improve functional outcomes in patients recovering from neurological insults or other conditions affecting swallowing function.

Passive Isotonic and active isotonic and isometric exercises were provided to the client. These exercises are depicted in Table 1

Table 1 Depicts Isotonic and Isometric Exercises

Exercises	Isometric Exercises	Isotonic Exercises
Lips	<p>The patient can be instructed to sustain an approximation of /u/ and /i/ for 10 secs.</p> <p>Once they are able to sustain, we can ask them to alternate between /u/ and /i/. *15 times/ day</p> <p>Range of Motion:</p> <p>1. Lip Retraction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Smile. Hold for 5 seconds. ● Relax and Repeat 5 times. 	<p>Lip Closure:</p> <p>1. Lip Press</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Press lips tightly together for 5 seconds. ● Relax and Repeat 5 times. <p>2. Lip Press on Tongue Depressor</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Tightly press lips around tongue depressor, while the clinician tries to remove it. ● Perform for 3 to 5 seconds. ● Relax and Repeat 5 times.

	<p>2. Lip Protrusion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pucker your lips as if you were going to kiss someone. ● Hold for 5 seconds. ● Relax and Repeat 5 times. <p>3. Lip Retraction and Protrusion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Smile then pucker your lips. Use exaggerated movements. <p>Relax and repeat 5 times</p>	<p>3. Puff Cheeks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fill cheeks with air, move air from one cheek to the other 5 to 10 times. ● No air should escape from around the lips or the nose. ● Relax and Repeat 5 times.
<p>Tongue</p>	<p>The patient can be instructed to lateralize the tongue movements (move left and right), Protrude and retract, elevation and depression. *15 times/ day</p> <p>Tongue Resistance:</p> <p>1. Tongue Push Forward</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Stick out your tongue as far as you can. ● Put something flat (back of a spoon or a tongue depressor) against your tongue ● Push against your tongue with the flat object at the same time as you push against the flat object with your tongue ● Hold for 1 to 2 seconds. ● Repeat 5 times. <p>2. Tongue Push Up</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Push down on your tongue with the flat object, while, at the same time, you push up with your tongue. ● Hold 1 second. ● Repeat 5 times. <p>3. Tongue Push To The Side</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Extend your tongue as far as possible to the corner of your mouth while pressing against a tongue depressor. ● Hold for 1 second. ● Repeat 5 times. ● (Repeat for each side of the mouth unless instructed otherwise). <p>4. Tongue Inside Push</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Put your finger against your right cheek about 1" to the side of the corner of your mouth. ● From the inside, push your tongue against your cheek where your finger is touching. Push as hard as you can. ● Hold it for 1 to 2 seconds. ● Relax and Repeat 5 times for each side of the mouth unless instructed otherwise 	<p>1. Tongue Extensions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Protrude tongue between lips. ● Sticking out tongue as far as you can. ● Hold tongue steady and straight for 3 to 5 seconds. ● Relax and Repeat 5 times. <p>2. Tongue Retraction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Retract tongue, touching the back of your tongue to the roof of your mouth (as if producing the /k/). ● Hold for 1 to 3 seconds. ● Relax and Repeat 5 times. <p>3. Tongue Extension and Retraction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Combine the two procedures above, holding each position for 1 to 3 seconds. ● Relax and Repeat 5 times. <p>4. Tongue Tip-Up</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Place tongue on the alveolar ridge, (the area behind your top teeth.) ● If you don't have any teeth, move your tongue tip up to your gum where your top teeth would be. ● Open mouth as wide as possible maintaining tongue contact. ● Hold for 3 to 5 seconds. ● Relax and Repeat 5 times <p>5. Tongue Elevation Along The Palate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Tongue tip to the alveolar ridge, (The area behind your top teeth.) ● Move tongue front to back along the roof of your mouth. ● Relax and Repeat 5 times. <p>6. Tongue Side To Side</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Tongue tip to the left side of the mouth, hold for 3 to 5 seconds. ● Tongue tip to the right side of the mouth, hold for 3 to 5 seconds. ● Relax and Repeat 5 to 10 times.

		<p>7. Tongue Tip-Up - Jaw Down</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If you can perform exercise # 4, lower your jaw as far as you can while keeping your tongue tip behind your teeth. • Hold your jaw in that position for 3 to 5 seconds <p>Relax and repeat 5 times.</p>
<p>Velum</p>	<p>To follow, the velopharyngeal sphincter is assessed, by asking the patient to puff out his/her cheeks; any air leakage through the nose can be checked by placing a small mirror under the patient's nose.</p> <p>The patient can be instructed to sustain production of /a/ *15 times/ day</p>	<p>-</p>
<p>Jaw</p>	<p>Jaw- The patient can be instructed to open and close their mouth</p>	<p>Range of Motion:</p> <p>1. Jaw Opening</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open your jaw as wide as you can until you feel a stretching, but no pain. • Hold this furthest open position for 5 seconds then relax and close your mouth. • Repeat this open posture 5 times. <p>2. Side-to-Side Movement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Move your jaw to the right side as far as you can until it pulls but does not hurt. • Hold it there for 5 seconds then relax. • Move your jaw to the left side as far as you can until you feel a stretch but it does not hurt. • Hold it there for 5 seconds then relax. • Alternate this right to left movement 5 times. <p>3. Increasing Circular Jaw Movement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Move your jaw around in a circle making it move as far in each direction as you can until you feel a stretch but no pain. • When you have completed a full circle relax. <p>Repeat the circular movement 5 times.</p>

Table 2: Depicts Direct Swallowing Intervention for Tracheostomy Patients

Swallow Impairment	Therapeutic Intervention Adaptation for trach/ Vent patients
<p>Low lung volumes</p> <p>(Facilitate Upper airway)</p>	<p><u>Costo-diaphragmatic breathing exercises:</u></p> <p>A. Slow inspiration through the nose, slow expiration through the mouth;</p> <p>B. Slow inspiration through the nose, expiration in 3, 4, 5 blows, through the mouth;</p> <p>C. Slow inspiration through the nose, fast expiration through the mouth;</p> <p>D. Slow inspiration through the nose, fast expiration with the articulation of an aphonous voice (preparatory exercise for arytenoid mobilization)</p>
Weak Cough Strength	Voluntary coughing tasks
Decreased vocal cord closure	<p>/Voluntary Breath Hold</p> <p>Adduction Exercises, Interrupted phonation, coughing and throat clearing</p> <p>Sustained phonation</p> <p>Supraglottic swallow</p>
Reduced laryngeal elevation	<p>Falsetto Exercises</p> <p>Mendelsohn Maneuver</p> <p>for laryngeal elevation and optimal airway closure during swallowing</p>
Weak pharyngeal wall constriction	<p>Masako maneuver/ Tongue resistance exercises</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sit or stand comfortably. 2. Stick your tongue out as far as is comfortable. 3. Hold your tongue gently between your front teeth, and then swallow. 4. Let go of your tongue. 5. Repeat these steps as many times as directed.
Multiple Swallows as a Therapy	Technique At one time or another most individuals engage in multiple swallows to clear a single bolus.

Tracheostomy Decannulation:

Following 12 weeks of intensive therapy, the patient successfully met the criteria for tracheostomy decannulation based on several key factors. Firstly, airway patency and integrity were ensured by the absence of excessive secretions that could not be effectively managed, indicating improved oropharyngeal and laryngeal anatomy essential for safe swallowing and a functional cough reflex. Secondly, the patient demonstrated the ability to breathe independently, achieving stable respiratory status without the need for ventilatory support. Cuff deflation trials were successfully tolerated, confirming adequate laryngeal function and the ability to manage secretions effectively. Furthermore, the patient exhibited enhanced airway protection and improved swallowing function.

allowing for the transition to capping of the tracheostomy tube. Additionally, significant progress in verbal communication abilities was observed, reflecting comprehensive rehabilitation efforts aimed at restoring cognitive and linguistic functions.

These achievements collectively supported the decision for tracheostomy decannulation, marking a significant milestone in the patient's recovery journey following severe traumatic brain injury.

The NG tube was subsequently removed, with ongoing language techniques such as semantic feature analysis, memory exercises, and augmentative and alternative communication methods.

The patient's rehabilitation yielded significant improvements in cognitive communication and swallowing function, facilitating successful weaning from mechanical ventilation and independence from artificial airway support. Continued cognitive and language stimulation supported ongoing recovery and adaptation to daily communication challenges. The case underscores the pivotal role of early, intensive SLP intervention in the neuro-ICU, emphasizing interdisciplinary collaboration and personalized rehabilitation strategies to optimize outcomes following severe TBI.

Conclusion:

Effective management of cognitive communication and swallowing deficits in severe TBI requires a comprehensive approach tailored to individual impairments and functional goals within the ICU setting. This case study highlights successful rehabilitation following extensive neurotrauma, emphasizing the critical role of early intervention, ongoing assessment, and collaborative care in achieving favorable clinical outcomes and enhancing quality of life.

Reference:

1. Yue JK, Vassar MJ, Lingsma HF, Cooper SR, Okonkwo DO, Valadka AB, et al. Transforming Research and Clinical Knowledge in Traumatic Brain Injury Pilot: Multicenter Implementation of the Common Data Elements for Traumatic Brain Injury. *Journal of Neurotrauma*. 2013 Nov 15;30(22):1831–44.
2. Terré R, Mearin F. Prospective evaluation of oro-pharyngeal dysphagia after severe traumatic brain injury. *Brain injury*. 2007 Jan 1;21(13-14):1411-7.
3. Morgan A, Ward E, Murdoch B. Clinical progression and outcome of dysphagia following paediatric traumatic brain injury: a prospective study. *Brain Injury*. 2004 Apr 1;18(4):359–76.
4. Alhashemi HH. Dysphagia in severe traumatic brain injury. *Neurosciences Journal*. 2010 Oct 1;15(4):231–6.
5. Schurr MJ, Ebner KA, Maser AL, Sperling KB, Helgerson RB, Harms B. Formal Swallowing Evaluation and Therapy after Traumatic Brain Injury Improves Dysphagia Outcomes. *Journal of Trauma and Acute Care Surgery*. 1999 May;46(5):817.
6. Mackay LE, Morgan AS, Bernstein BA. Factors Affecting Oral Feeding with Severe Traumatic Brain Injury. *The Journal of Head Trauma Rehabilitation*. 1999 Oct;14(5):435.